

Enhancing Video Conferences with Multi-Speaker Transcription and Summarization

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Abstract—Efficient collaboration during video conferences is crucial for team productivity. However, the absence of effective mechanisms to capture and preserve key insights often results in misunderstandings and reduced efficiency. The proposed initiative focuses on developing an application to improve collaboration in video conferences by converting speech conversations into summarized text. Leveraging machine learning models, the system transcribes spoken content using a transcription model and employs abstractive summarization using a summarization model. The transcription architecture is implemented as an encoder-decoder Transformer. Input audio is split into small chunks, converted into a log-Mel spectrogram, and then passed into an encoder. A decoder is trained to predict the corresponding text caption, intermixed with special tokens that direct the model to perform transcription. Summarization model utilizes an encoder to understand the input text and a decoder to generate the summary. The goal is to empower users to effortlessly capture and retain crucial discussions, promoting better understanding and decision-making. By providing a comprehensive solution, this initiative seeks to mitigate misunderstandings and elevate productivity in contemporary workplaces.

Index Terms—Index Terms—Conversation summarization, FLAN-T5, Multi-speaker transcription, ROUGE metrics, SAM-Sum dataset, Speaker identification, Transformer architecture, Video conferencing, WebRTC.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary digital landscape, video conferencing platforms have emerged as indispensable tools for facilitating modern communication, bridging geographical divides, and fostering collaboration across diverse teams. These platforms have become particularly vital in remote work, educational settings, and global business interactions, enabling real-time interaction through audio and video streams. However, despite their widespread adoption, most existing video conferencing solutions suffer from a significant limitation: the inability to effectively preserve and distill the wealth of content generated during discussions. This deficiency often results in missed insights, misunderstandings among participants, and reduced overall productivity, as critical information is not systematically captured or readily accessible post-meeting.

To address these shortcomings and revolutionize the landscape of video conferencing, an innovative multispeaker transcription and summarization system is introduced to enhance

understanding and collaboration among participants. The primary objective is to develop an application that not only facilitates real-time communication but also empowers users to capture, retain, and leverage key insights from their discussions. At its core, the system integrates advanced transcription capabilities to generate detailed multi-speaker transcripts, assigning speaker labels to each segment of dialogue. This feature ensures that every participant's contribution is clearly identified and documented, enabling comprehensive understanding and minimizing confusion in multi-participant settings.

Beyond transcription, the system incorporates a sophisticated summarization model to distill conversational speech into concise, coherent summaries that encapsulate the main ideas and critical points of the discussion. These conversation summaries, along with the multi-speaker transcripts, can be dynamically broadcasted to all meeting participants, eliminating the need for manual note-taking and allowing users to focus on the discussion itself. By incorporating these features, the application not only saves time but also enhances accessibility, enabling participants to effortlessly review and comprehend the essence of meetings, even after they conclude.

To further enrich the collaborative experience, the application includes an integrated chatting facility, allowing users to exchange thoughts and ideas in real-time during the video conference. Administrative users can broadcast generated summaries to ensure alignment and clarity across all participants. This multifaceted approach transforms the video conferencing experience, making it more interactive, efficient, and productive.

Technically, the application leverages a robust technological stack to achieve these goals. The frontend is developed using React.js, providing a responsive and user-friendly interface. On the backend, a Flask application serves the machine learning models responsible for transcription and summarization, while Express.js handles WebRTC integration to enable high-quality audio and video streaming. WebRTC, a key technology in this system, ensures low-latency, real-time communication, underpinning the capture and processing of multi-speaker audio channels. Together, these components create a seamless, end-to-end solution that harnesses the power of machine

learning and web technologies to deliver a transformative video conferencing tool.

By providing multi-speaker transcripts and meeting summaries, this application empowers users to extract valuable insights from their discussions, fostering deeper understanding, informed decision-making, and enhanced collaboration. By automating the documentation process, the application frees individuals from the burden of note-taking, allowing them to focus on contributing ideas, asking questions, and driving discussions forward.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Following are some of the works related to speaker identification, summarisation, transcription tasks:

The Whisper transcription model[1] is designed to accurately convert audio into text. Trained on a vast dataset of 680,000 hours of audio, it demonstrates exceptional efficiency in generating precise transcripts. Compared to previous models, Whisper has achieved superior performance, making it a highly reliable solution for transcription tasks.

The SAMSSum Corpus [2], a dataset specifically designed for abstractive dialogue summarization tasks. The dataset is prepared using everyday human conversations with corresponding manually written summaries. Most of the abstractive summarization model for generating conversation summary are trained using the SAMSum dataset.

The DialogSum dataset [3] is designed to generate concise summaries of conversations. It contains over 13,000 examples, each featuring human-written summaries for various types of dialogues. To evaluate its effectiveness, it is tested using a BERT model, which significantly improved the quality and coherence of the generated summaries.

PEGASUS model [4] help with text summarization. It learns by hiding important sentences and then trying to guess them. PEGASUS combines two methods to make better summaries and worked really well on different types of texts like news, laws, and science papers. It was better than many other models, it used Mask Language Modeling, gap sentence generation techniques to prepare the abstract summaries.

BART [6] learning consists of changing the text in random ways and then trying to fix it back to normal. It uses a special Transformer based architecture. Even though it is simple, BART is powerful. It combines ideas from BERT which reads both sides of a sentence and GPT which reads from left to right.

T5 model [6] that turns all language tasks into a text-making problem. This makes it easy to train for things like summarization, translation, and answering questions. T5 did better than many other models and got high scores on different tests.

FLAN-T5 [7], a better version of T5 that learns from many different tasks and datasets. It is trained to follow instructions and can do well even with little or no examples. FLAN-T5 is more useful for different language tasks.

A comprehensive overview of the progress in speaker diarization is provided in [12], with a focus on deep learning-

based approaches. It discusses the key components of diarization systems, including voice activity detection (VAD), speaker embedding extraction, clustering, and end-to-end neural diarization.

A study focused at different summarization models[8] provides an analysis of Abstractive Text Summarization Models. The paper compares models like PEGASUS, T5, and BART on performing abstractive summarisation, which give results of getting high scores on tests like ROUGE and BLEU. Thus helped to understand the current summarization models used in making summaries.

[10] explores WebRTC technology, detailing the implementation of WebRTC clients, servers, and signaling mechanisms. It explains the key components of the WebRTC API and their functionalities. Since WebRTC standards do not define specific signaling methods or protocols, this research introduces and implements a novel signaling approach. A message sequence chart illustrates the communication flow between peers and the server. The server application is built as a WebSocket server, while the client application showcases the use of the WebRTC API to enable real-time communication. Additionally, the study highlights the advantages of WebRTC and discusses potential future developments.

The SAMSum and DialogSum datasets were designed for training models to generate concise conversation summaries. Models like PEGASUS, BART, and T5 have demonstrated strong performance in text summarization using advanced techniques such as masked language modeling and sentence reconstruction. FLAN-T5 further improved upon T5 by enhancing instruction-following capabilities. Comparative studies have shown that these models achieve high ROUGE and BLEU scores.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

Fig. 1. Existing Model Architecture

The existing system in figure 1 consists of a single-speaker transcription[1] and summarization module[4] designed to capture spoken language, convert it into text, and generate concise summaries based on the transcribed content. This module performs exceptionally well in scenarios where a single speaker talks continuously, such as lectures, presentations, or monologues, ensuring accurate transcriptions and meaningful summaries. However, its effectiveness diminishes in multi-speaker environments, such as group discussions or meetings, where multiple participants speak intermittently or simultaneously.

The process begins with an audio input, which is converted into a log Mel spectrogram. This spectrogram is then fed into the transformer model, which consists of multiple encoder and decoder blocks. The encoder processes the spectrogram to extract meaningful features, and the decoder generates the corresponding text transcription. Transformer-based[1] architecture enables accurate speech recognition, capturing linguistic and acoustic patterns efficiently.

Once the transcribed text is generated, it is passed to the transformer model[4] for summarization. It consists of an encoder-decoder architecture, where the encoder processes the input text and the decoder generates a concise summary. The encoder extracts relevant information, filtering out unnecessary details, while the decoder constructs a coherent and meaningful summary. This pipeline ensures that lengthy speech data is effectively transcribed and summarized, making it easier to analyze and interpret key information.

T5 [6], can transform all language tasks into a unified text-to-text framework, where input text is processed to produce conversation summaries as output. In this system, the T5 base model, with its encoder-decoder architecture, processes the transcribed text to generate coherent, abstractive summaries.

The proposed system builds upon existing systems by transcribing multi-speaker conversations and generating conversation summaries, achieving metric scores that surpass all existing summarization models.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for multi-speaker transcription, speaker identification, and summarization involves the following steps. Figure 2 illustrates the architecture of the system.

A. Audio Input captured through WebRTC

Audio channel of multiple speakers conversing in video conference will be captured and analysed[10]. The audio of multiple speakers is captured and stored as a single audio file.

B. Generate transcription with Timestamps

The .wav audio file is transcribed into text using a transcription model[1]. The output includes text segments with corresponding timestamps.

C. Segmentation and Embedding Extraction

The audio file is divided into smaller segments for making embeddings. Speaker embeddings are extracted from each segment for capturing unique voice characteristics to distinguish speakers.

D. Clustering the embeddings

A clustering algorithm is applied to the extracted embeddings[12] to group segments by speaker. Speaker labels are assigned to each segment based on the clustering output. Based on the timestamps each transcription segment is assigned with proper speaker tags.

E. Speaker Tag to Speaker name Mapping

The system maintains an array of active speakers. This is done by analysing the audio channel of the device using webRTC [10]. Each logged in user will be having separate audio channel, analysing which audio channel contributes to more than a particular threshold will be considered as the active speaker. Each speaker tag is mapped to the corresponding speaker's name using the prepared active speaker array. Active speaker array contains the name of the user who talked during the conversation in order.

F. Text Segmentation by Speaker

The transcribed text is organized by speaker, with each speaker's name prepended to their respective dialogue.

G. Summarization

The processed speaker-wise text is input into a summarization model. The model's encoder-decoder architecture[7] generates a concise summary of the conversation.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Figure 2 represents a multi-speaker transcription and summarization system designed to process audio input from WebRTC-based communication. It captures multiple audio channels and follows two parallel processing paths: active speaker identification and speaker segmentation with transcription. The figure 2 illustrates a component of the active speaker identification system designed for video conferencing, which enhances participant engagement by dynamically identifying and tracking active speakers in real-time. This process begins with analyzing the audio channel of each connected speaker, captured via WebRTC, to monitor the frequency of their audio input. The system employs a decision point where the audio frequency is compared against a threshold limit; if the frequency exceeds this threshold, indicating active speech, the name of the corresponding user is appended to an active speaker array. This array, prepared and maintained throughout the conference, dynamically lists the names of individuals

Fig. 2. Architecture

currently speaking, enabling efficient speaker tracking and facilitating features like multi-speaker transcription and summarization. By leveraging this frequency-based approach, the system ensures accurate identification of active participants, improving the clarity and context of meeting discussions. Simultaneously, the entire conversation is processed as a single audio file, where an encoder-decoder model transcribes the speech with timestamps. To distinguish different speakers, the system segments the audio, extracts speaker embeddings, and applies clustering techniques to assign appropriate speaker labels. The generated multi-speaker transcript, containing timestamps and speaker tags, undergoes a mapping process to replace generic speaker identifiers with actual names. Finally, a summarization model condenses the transcript into a structured meeting summary, improving accessibility and efficiency in virtual meetings, online discussions.

A. Transformer for Transcription

The transcription task is achieved with the help of transformer architecture comprising encoder and decoder. The architecture of the transcription system is illustrated in figure 3. The encoder is responsible for converting the audio features into particular meaningful representations[1]. In order to capture the contextual information self-attention mechanism is used, it helps the model to weigh the importance of each input token.

Fig. 3. Transcription Model Architecture

To enhance the transcription process, the decoder also employs a transformer-based architecture with self-attention and cross-attention mechanisms. The self-attention mechanism allows

the decoder to focus on relevant parts of the previously generated text, ensuring fluency and coherence in the transcription. The cross-attention mechanism, on the other hand, enables the decoder to attend to the encoded audio representations, ensuring that the generated text remains aligned with the original speech. Additionally, a masked self-attention mechanism is used to prevent the model from looking ahead at future tokens, thereby ensuring autoregressive generation. Using multiple attention heads make the model capture the diverse relationships effectively. The order of words in a sentence really matters, so positional encoding is done to capture the information about positioning of tokens in a sequence. By incorporating multiple layers of transformer blocks in encoder, it captures both low and high level information. The final layer of encoder thus produces a contextualised representation of the input audio features. The contextualised information will be passed on to the decoder. At each step, considering the previously generated token, it predicts the next word in the transcription sequence.

B. Transformer for Summarization

In order to train the summarization model SAMSum Dataset[2] which contains conversation text and corresponding human-written summaries were used. A fine tuned version of Flan T5 model[7] which is an improved version of T5 base model[6] is used for generating the meeting summary. First the Flan T5 model was finetuned with SAMSum dataset. The architecture of the summarization system is illustrated in figure 4. The encoder captures the relationship between words within the text, capturing the context and meaning. Through repeated computation, the encoder refines the important information contained in the input text into a compressed representation, effectively summarizing its content[4]. Subsequently, the decoder takes on the task of creating the summary text based on the encoded representation produced by the encoder. By using another set of Transformer blocks with attention mechanisms, the decoder attends to the output of encoder, retrieving suitable information for summarizing the text. In a step-by-step fashion, each decoder layer generates one word or phrase at a time, progressively building the summary. Techniques such as gap sentence generation and masked language modeling into the decoder's architecture[2] can enhance the quality and coherence of the generated summary. These techniques enable the decoder to fill in missing information, predict the next word or phrase based on context, and ensure that the generated summary maintains syntactic and semantic coherence. Finetuning is performed by first loading the SAMSum dataset, which is then split into train, validation, and test sets. The Flan-T5 [7] model and its tokenizer are then loaded. Each dialogue and its corresponding summary are converted into a tokenized format. To manage the learning rate, warmup steps are set, gradually increasing the learning rate during the initial steps. Overall, the association between the encoder and decoder components in the summarization process makes the model to transform the complex textual information into concise and coherent summaries, thus facilitates in efficient information retrieval and comprehension.

Fig. 4. Summarization Model Architecture

VI. RESULT ANALYSIS

The performance of both the transcription and summarization models is evaluated based on various metrics and qualitative assessments. For the transcription model, metrics such as WER (word error rate) are computed to quantify the model's ability to accurately transcribe audio input to text[1]. Furthermore, the summarization model's performance is assessed using metrics such as ROUGE scores (RecallOriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation), which measure the overlap between generated summaries and reference summaries. Manual inspection of summarized data was also done.

A. Experimental Setup

The abstractive summarization model is made by finetuning on SAMSum dataset to generate conversation summaries. The evaluation was conducted on the test set of the SAMSum dataset, which contains human-annotated dialogues with corresponding reference summaries. The summarization process used the pipeline function from the Hugging Face Transformers library for generating predictions.

B. Parameters to Evaluate – Multi Speaker Transcript

The transcription model demonstrates robust performance in speech recognition, achieving a Word Error Rate (WER) [1] of 2.7 on the LibriSpeech clean dataset, matching state-of-the-art systems like wav2vec 2.0. Notably, it outperforms other models on diverse datasets, with an average relative error reduction (RER) of 55.2 compared to wav2vec 2.0, and achieves a WER of 25.5 on the CHiME-6 dataset versus 65.8 for wav2vec 2.0. In long-form transcription tasks, model maintains competitive performance with WERs ranging from 3.42 to 22.0, showcasing its robustness and generalization capabilities in real-world scenarios.

C. Evaluation Metrics for Summarization

The performance of the model was evaluated using multiple metrics to assess the quality of the generated summaries in comparison to human-written references.

- **ROUGE**: The primary evaluation metric used was ROUGE which measures word overlap and provides insights into three key aspects:
 - **ROUGE-1 (Unigram Overlap)**: Evaluates content fidelity by measuring the overlap of individual words between the generated summary and the reference.
 - **ROUGE-2 (Bigram Overlap)**: Captures fluency and coherence by comparing sequences of two consecutive words in the generated and reference summaries.
 - **ROUGE-L (Longest Common Subsequence)**: Assesses syntactic similarity by identifying the longest common word sequence between the summaries.
- **METEOR**: Unlike ROUGE, METEOR considers synonymy, stemming, and word order, making it more effective in capturing semantic equivalence between the generated and reference summaries.
- **BERTScore**: This metric leverages contextual embeddings rather than relying solely on lexical similarity. It evaluates summaries at a deeper semantic level by computing similarity scores based on pre-trained transformer models. BERTScore provides three key measurements:
 - **Precision**: Precision measures the proportion of the generated summary’s content that is semantically relevant to the reference summary.
 - **Recall**: Recall measures the proportion of semantically important concepts or ideas from the reference summary that are present in the generated abstractive summary.
 - **F1 Score**: A balanced measure that combines both precision and recall, reflecting overall performance.

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE ROUGE SCORES FOR SUMMARIZATION MODELS ON SAMSUM DATASET

Model	ROUGE-1	ROUGE-2	ROUGE-L
google/pegasus-cnn-dailymail	38.26	10.69	33.76
T5-base	33.11	9.16	29.38
facebook/bart-large-cnn	40.63	13.16	36.38
proposed model	45.98	22.44	36.67

TABLE II
COMPARATIVE METEOR SCORES FOR SUMMARIZATION MODELS ON SAMSUM DATASET

Model	METEOR
google/pegasus-cnn-dailymail	28.69
T5-base	26.79
facebook/bart-large-cnn	34.41
proposed model	45.98

TABLE III
COMPARATIVE BERT SCORES FOR SUMMARIZATION MODELS ON SAMSUM DATASET

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
google/pegasus-cnn-dailymail	44.44	58.18	50.10
T5-base	48.16	55.40	51.25
facebook/bart-large-cnn	47.90	62.33	53.86
proposed model	66.22	71.63	68.47

Fig. 5. Model Training Loss Over Iterations

Fig. 6. ROUGE Scores Comparison

These results in Table I indicate that the model successfully captures relevant information from dialogue text and translates it into concise and meaningful summaries. Figure 5 illustrates a downward trend in the training loss, indicating

Fig. 7. METEOR Scores Comparison

Fig. 8. BERT Scores Comparison

that the model's performance improves as training progresses. Table I compares the results achieved by the different models using rouge score. Notably, the ROUGE-1 score surpasses that of BART-large-CNN, which achieves a ROUGE-1 score of 40.63[9]. Table II compares the results achieved by the different models using METEOR score. Table III compares the results achieved by the different models using Bert score. Figure 6 presents a graph comparing the ROUGE scores of the proposed model against existing models. Figure 7 illustrates a comparison of METEOR scores between the proposed model and existing models. Figure 8 shows a graph comparing the BERT scores of the proposed model with existing models.

VII. CONCLUSION

Existing Video conferencing platforms can be revolutionised by incorporating the transcription and summarization functionalities using the transformer encoder-decoder architecture. The primary objective was to develop a platform that not only facilitates real-time communication but also enhances productivity through transcription and summarization of conversations. The main objective was to develop an application for enhancing communication. The system enhances the productivity by incorporating the transcription and summarization models. The active speaker is identified by analysing the audio channel of webRTC. Multispeaker transcript and conversation summary retains the important information and thus increases the collaboration. The summarization model is found to have a rouge score of 45.98 which surpasses existing models.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

Future work could focus on developing real-time transcription and summarization to provide instantaneous feedback during meetings, integrating multi-modal analysis (e.g., video-based gestures and facial expressions) for richer summaries, scaling the system for large-scale conferences using distributed computing, expanding language and dialect support for global applicability, enhancing privacy and security with end-to-end encryption, and integrating with collaboration tools for seamless adoption, thereby positioning this solution as a transformative tool for modern video conferencing productivity and engagement worldwide.

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